

Annotated checklist of the Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) of Mali

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Abstract

Fifty-three species of Cerambycidae were collected in Mali between 2014 and 2020 as by-catches within NIH and IVCC projects for malaria vector ecology and control, 42 of them are new records for the country. An updated list of 89 species of cerambycid beetles of Mali is presented. Two species, *Niphotragulus occidentalis* Breuning, 1977 and *Sophronica sudanica* Breuning, 1962, are so far only known from Mali.

Keywords

Climate change, deforestation, faunistic list, vegetation zones, West Africa

Introduction

The Republic of Mali is a fast-developing West African country with an area of 1.2 million km² and a quickly growing population of approximately 20 million (UN 2022). The territory stretches from north to south for a 1600 km distance and occupies five main ecological climate and vegetation zones (Rian et al. 2009; Coulibaly et al. 2016; Tandina et al. 2018; Sylla 2020): Saharan, Sahelian, Sudanian, Sudano-Guinean and Guinean zones (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Vegetation zones and annual precipitation with the collecting sites (red for the original data, blue for the references) on a satellite view of Mali (Google, 2022). Locus “Kangaba+” includes closely situated Déguéla, Kangaba, Kenieroba and Ouronina.

The vast northern areas include extreme desert, semidesert, and some oasis habitats with a very low population density of nomadic and semi-nomadic herders. Here the climate is typical of the Sahara Desert, and July is the hottest month. It rarely rains, though every few years some sporadic and local downpours can occur. More

to the south, in the center of the country, in July, August, and September, the temperature decreases steadily because of the regular showers fed by the African summer monsoon, which brings humid currents from the Atlantic Ocean. Here the climate is also tropical in winter, and the hottest months are April, May, and June, when the maximum temperature often exceeds 40°C, with peaks of 48°C, this area is a part of the Sahel. In the southern region, rainfall exceeds 500 mm per year (south of a line along the border of Senegal to Mopti), and in the extreme south (in a line from Bamako to Sikasso), it exceeds 1,000 mm with the rainy season lasting from June to November (WMO 2021).

The country as a whole suffers from desertification slowly moving from north to south and intensive human-caused accelerating deforestation, especially in the southern regions (FAO UN / UN EP 2020). The climate change is pushing on an annual basis the Sahara Desert up to 48 km towards the south in the Sahel, and once reliable rainy seasons are now fluctuating in time and total annual amounts of precipitation significantly, resulting in more intensive use of remaining ecosystems suitable for agriculture (Nicholson 2000; Nicholson 2001; Thomas et Nigam 2018).

In Mali deforestation is mainly driven by replacing woodlands with agricultural areas, but also logging for timber and clearing bushland and remaining forests for charcoal production in areas that can later not be used for agriculture like steep slopes and rocky areas is common practice (Mensah et al. 2020). The degradation of the remaining forests is further driven by overgrazing of cattle, sheep, and goats and burning annually the undergrowth at the end of the dry season to enhance fresh growth for grazing (Kiyani et al. 2017). In Malian villages firewood is still the main energy source for cooking and forests are accordingly cleaned out of any type of dead wood (Morton 2007). Accordingly, insect groups that are dependent on mature woodlands, especially fallen trees are strongly impacted and their habitats are quickly vanishing. One of the vulnerable groups is Cerambycidae, especially species that are xylophagous and develop inside the wood and roots of large trees.

Very little was so far known about the Cerambycidae of Mali – only one article was devoted to the fauna of the country by Villiers (1962) mentioning 31 taxa. Other records from Mali are sporadic without an attempt to summarize the local fauna (Pic 1898; Pic 1932; Lapesme 1952; Lapesme et Breuning 1958; Villiers 1962; Breuning 1962b; Breuning 1977; Breuning 1963; Quentin et Villiers 1971; Quentin et Villiers 1972; Sudre et al. 2007; Juhel et Bentanachs 2009; Teocchi et al. 2016; Juhel 2017; Bjørnstad 2019).

Material and methods

The material of the present study was obtained from by-catches from long-term malaria research conducted from 2008 to 2021 by the University of Sciences, Techniques, and Technologies of Bamako (USTTB). Adults were collected with sweep nets, Malaise traps, UV-CDC traps, and different types of larger UV traps (Kline et

al. 2011; Sheikh et al. 2016) and by other miscellaneous methods by the local and visiting entomologists around the following localities (Figs 2–4): Bamako, Déguéla, Kangaba, Kenieroba, Mopti, Ouronina, Sikasso. The collected material was identified and stored partially in the first author's collection and collection of the USTTB.

Species list

Subfamily Philinae, Tribe Philini

1. *Doesus telephoroides* Pascoe, 1862

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, Ethiopia, Mali, Nigeria, Senegal, Sudan; also recorded from India and Laos (Pascoe 1862; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo, 12.VI.1960 (Villiers 1962).

Subfamily Prioninae, Tribe Prionini

2. *Polyarthron pectinicornis* (Fabricius, 1793)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Polyarthron Faure-Bigueti* Pic, 1898

= *Prionus pectinicornis* Gaillardii Lameere, 1912

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Mali, Mauritania, Morocco, Niger, Senegal, Western Sahara (Fabricius 1793; Pic 1898; Lameere 1912a; Rungs 1947; Quentin 1956; Villiers 1961; Löbl et Smetana 2010; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Timbuktu (Pic 1898).

Subfamily Prioninae, Tribe Macrotomini

3. *Mallodon downesii* Hope, 1843

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Mallodon laevipenne* White, 1853

= *Mallodon costipenne* White, 1853

= *Mallodon plagiatum* Thomson, 1867

= *Mallodon proximum* Thomson, 1867

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Benin, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Ethiopia, Gabon, the Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Liberia, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Rwanda, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe; also recorded from Comoros, Costa Rica, Madagascar (Hope 1843; White 1853; Thomson 1867; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo, 2.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962), Bamako, 20.VIII.2018 (original data).

4. *Macrotoma palmata* (Fabricius, 1792)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Prionus senegalensis* Olivier, 1795
- = *Prionus spinipes* Illiger, 1805
- = *Macrotoma humeralis* White, 1853
- = *Macrotoma Valida* Thomson, 1877
- = *Macrotoma palmata* var. *rugulosa* Kolbe, 1894
- = *Macrotoma palmata* var. *brevipes* Kolbe, 1894
- = *Macrotoma Böhmi* Reitter, 1903

Distribution in Africa: Algeria, Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, Djibouti, DR Congo, Egypt, Equatorial Guinea, Eritrea, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Ethiopia, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe; also recorded from Mauritius, Saudi Arabia, Yemen (Fabricius 1792; Olivier 1795; Illiger 1805; White 1853; Thomson 1877; Kolbe 1894; Reitter 1903; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo; Niafunke, 5.VII.1960 (Villiers 1962); Déguéla, 12.VI.2016 (original data).

5. *Aulacopus reticulatus* Audinet-Serville, 1832

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Aulacopus natalensis* White, 1853
- = *Aulacopus natalensis* var. *impressicollis* Kolbe, 1898

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Botswana, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Mali, Mozambique, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe (Audinet-Serville 1832; White 1853; Kolbe 1898; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962).

Figures 2–4. Habitats near collection sites: **2.** Open rocky savanna nearby Ouronina. **3.** Woody lowland near Ouronina. **4.** Collecting on a white screen in the middle of a riverine forest nearby Déguéla.

6. *Navosomopsis feisthameli* (Buquet, 1860)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Macrotoma novemcostata* Quedenfeldt, 1882
- = *Macrotoma (Navosomopsis) ivoriensis* Lepesme, 1953
- = *Macrotoma (Navosomopsis) ebororae* Gilmour, 1956

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Benin, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Tanzania, Togo (Buquet 1860; Quedenfeldt 1882; Lepesme 1953b; Gilmour 1956b; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Kangaba, 3–7.VII.2016.

Subfamily Prioninae, Tribe Acanthophorini

7. *Tithoes confinis* (Laporte de Castelnau, 1840)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Tithoes mandibularis* Thomson, 1877
- = *Tithoes Intermedius* Thomson, 1877
- = *Tithoës crassipes* Quedenfeldt, 1882
- = *Tithoes falcatus* Kolbe, 1898
- = *Tithoes gularis* Kolbe, 1898
- = *Tithoes gnatho* Kolbe, 1898
- = *Tithoes longicornis* Kolbe, 1898

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Botswana, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Djibouti, DR Congo, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Guinea, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mozambique, Namibia, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe; also recorded from Saudi Arabia (Laporte de Castelnau 1840; Thomson 1877; Quedenfeldt 1882; Kolbe 1898; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962); Kangaba 5.vii.2016 (original data).

Subfamily Prioninae, Tribe Cantharocnemini

8. *Cantharocnemis (Cantharoplatys) plicipennis* Fairmaire, 1887

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Gabon, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Sierra Leone, Tanzania (Fairmaire 1887b; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, 5.VI.2016.

9. *Cantharocnemis spondyloides* Audinet-Serville, 1832

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Hoploscelis lucanoides* Audinet-Serville, 1832
- = *Cantharocnemis variolosus* Fairmaire, 1882
- = *Cantharocnemis latibula* Fairmaire, 1882
- = *Cantharocnemis obockianus* Fairmaire, 1890
- = *Cantharocnemis modestus* Fairmaire, 1897
- = *Cantharocnemis* (*Cantharocnemis*) *Gahani* Lameere, 1902
- = *Cantharocnemis Grandidieri* Lameere, 1912
- = *Cantharocnemis* (*Cantharofodius*) *migsi* Gilmour, 1956
- = *Cantharocnemis arabicus* Fuchs, 1969

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Djibouti, Egypt, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Guinea, Kenya, Mali, Mauritania, Namibia, Niger, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Yemen, Zimbabwe; also recorded from Oman, Saudi Arabia and Yemen (Audinet-Serville 1832; Fairmaire 1882a; Fairmaire 1882b; Fairmaire 1890; Fairmaire 1897; Lameere 1902; Lameere 1912b; Gilmour 1956b; Fuchs 1969; Quentin et Simonetta 1992; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Quentin et Simonetta 1992; Adlbauer et Beck 2015); Sikasso, VIII.2015 (original data).

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Oemini

10. *Calybistum lugubre* (Olivier, 1790)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Calybistum Fuliginosum* Thomson, 1878

Distribution in Africa: Central African Republic, Ethiopia, the Gambia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mali, Nigeria, Senegal, Sudan, Uganda (Olivier 1790; Thomson 1878; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 7.VIII.1956; Dogo (Villiers 1962); Ouronina, VIII.2020 (original data).

11. *Enicoeme krelli* Adlbauer, 2003

Distribution in Africa: Ivory Coast, Nigeria (Adlbauer 2003; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Mopti, VI.2014.

12. *Paroeme flava* (Thomson, 1858)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Paroeme laevicollis* Aurivillius, 1927

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Congo, Gabon, Mali, Nigeria (Thomson 1858; Aurivillius 1927; Breuning 1962c; Villiers 1962; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Farimaké – Dioura, 19.VII.1954 (Villiers 1962).

13. *Hypoeshrus (Tibestia) dallonii* Peyerimhoff, 1936

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Hypoeshrus strigosus* v. *rungsi* Lepesme et Breuning, 1955

= *Hypoeshrus strigosus* v. *peyerimhoffi* Lepesme et Breuning, 1955

= *Hypoeshrus abyssinicus* v. *gyllenhali* Lepesme et Breuning, 1955

= *Hypoeshrus abyssinicus* sbsp. *dallonii* v. *mirei* Lepesme et Breuning, 1955

= *Hypoeshrus abyssinicus* sbsp. *dallonii* v. *wittei* Lepesme et Breuning, 1955

= *Hypoeshrus strigosus* v. *pallidipes* Quentin, 1956

Distribution in Africa: Algeria, Burkina Faso, Chad, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Libya, Mali, Mauritania, Morocco, Niger, Senegal, Sudan, Uganda (Peyerimhoff 1936; Lepesme et Breuning 1955c; Quentin 1956; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Adlbauer et Beck 2015).

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe O브리ni**14. *Ossibia fuscata* (Chevrolat, 1856)**

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Adiaphorus crinitus* Fåhraeus, 1872

= *Obriaccum Senegalense* Thomson, 1878

= *Ossibia fuscata* v. *rubra* Quentin, 1956

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Djibouti, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Zimbabwe; also recorded from Yemen (Chevrolat 1856; Fåhraeus 1872; Thomson 1878; Lepesme 1952a; Quentin 1956; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962).

15. *Ossibia murina* (Gerstäcker, 1855)

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Zimbabwe (Gerstäcker 1855; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 13.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962).

16. *Oxilus terminatus* Buquet, 1859

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Oxilus terminatus* v. *miréi* Quentin, 1956

= *Oxilus terminatus* var. *abyssinicus* Breuning, 1957

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Ethiopia, Kenya, Mali, Mozambique, Senegal, Sudan, Uganda (Buquet 1859; Quentin 1956; Breuning 1957a; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 7.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962).

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Xystrocerini

17. *Xystrocera dispar* (Fåhraeus, 1872)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Xystrocera curticolis* Fairmaire, 1882

= *Xystrocera nitidiventris* Fairmaire, 1887

= *Xystrocera parvicollis* Fairmaire, 1892

Distribution in Africa: Botswana, Burkina Faso, Central African Republic, Chad, Djibouti, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zimbabwe and Mali (**new record**); also recorded from Saudi Arabia (Fåhraeus 1872; Fairmaire 1882; Fairmaire 1887a; Fairmaire 1892b; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, 5.VI.2016.

Taxonomic note: Externally similar to 19. *Xystrocera vittata* (Fabricius, 1792), species relation should be reconsidered.

18. *Xystrocera nigrita* Audinet-Serville, 1834

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Benin, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Liberia, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal,

Sierra Leone, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda (Audinet-Serville 1834; Villiers 1962; Martins 1980; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962); Ouronina, 5.VI.2016, VIII.2020 (original data).

19. *Xystrocera vittata* (Fabricius, 1792)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Xystrocera senegalensis* Klug, 1835

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Cameroon, Congo, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Liberia, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Sudan, Togo (Fabricius 1792; Klug 1835; Villiers 1962; Quentin et Villiers 1979; Martins 1980; Joly et al. 2008; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Farimaké – Dioura, 6.VII.1954 (Villiers 1962).

Taxonomic note: Externally similar to 17. *Xystrocera dispar* (Fahraeus, 1872), species relations should be reconsidered.

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Cerambycini

20. *Taurotagus griseus* (Guérin-Ménéville, 1844)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Taurotagus Auberti* Fairmaire, 1892

= *Taurotagus Greenfieldi* Gahan, 1894

Distribution in Africa: DR Congo, Djibouti, Egypt, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mali, Senegal, Somalia, Sudan, Tanzania; also recorded from Yemen (Guérin-Ménéville 1844; Fairmaire 1892; Gahan 1894; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962).

21. *Taurotagus impressus* Duffy, 1955

Distribution in Africa: Rwanda (Duffy 1955; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015; Ouronina, VIII.2020.

22. *Neoplocaederus glabricollis* (Hope, 1843)

Distribution in Africa: Central African Republic, Liberia (Hope 1843; White 1853; Teocchi 1993; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015.

23. *Neoplocaederus viridescens* (Atkinson, 1953)

Distribution in Africa: DR Congo, the Gambia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Senegal, Sierra Leone (Atkinson 1953; Adlbauer 1993; Adlbauer 2000; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VII.2016.

24. *Neoplocaederus denticornis* (Fabricius, 1801)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Plocederus cribrithorax* Kolbe, 1897

= *Plocaederus atlanticus* Rungs, 1953

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Cameroon, Chad, DR Congo, Djibouti, Ethiopia, the Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mali, Morocco, Mozambique, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Zimbabwe; also recorded from Oman, Saudi Arabia and Yemen (Fabricius 1801; Kolbe 1897; Kotán et Sama 2011; Rungs 1953; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Trócoli 2019, Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962); Ouronina, VIII.2020.

25. *Neoplocaederus cyanipennis* (Thomson, 1861)

Distribution in Africa: Angola, DR Congo, Ethiopia, the Gambia, Ivory Coast, Niger, Senegal (Thomson 1861; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

26. *Derolus arciferus* (Gahan, 1891)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Derolus* (s. s.) *nigritulus* Breuning, 1978

= *Derolus* (s. s.) *girardi* Breuning, 1978

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Central African Republic, DR Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Ethiopia, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Malawi, Mozambique, Niger, Senegal, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo. (Gahan 1891; Breuning 1978a; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

27. *Derolus subaureus* (Jordan, 1894)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Derolus (Derolus) pseudoaureus* Lepesme et Breuning, 1958

= *Derolus* (s. str.) *togoensis* Breuning, 1974

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Burkina Faso, Central African Republic, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mali, Niger, Senegal, Sudan, Togo (Jordan 1894; Lepesme et Breuning 1958; Villiers 1962; Breuning 1974b; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Kouloba (Lepesme et Breuning 1958); Kara, 16.V.1959 (Villiers 1962); Ouronina 7.VI.2016 (original data).

28. *Dissaporus cachani* (Lepesme et Breuning, 1958)

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Cameroon, Gabon, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Togo (Lepesme et Breuning 1958; Adlbauer 2006b; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VI.2020.

29. *Sudreana rugosa* Adlbauer, 2006

Distribution in Africa: Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast (Adlbauer 2006a; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Hesperophanini**30. *Tropicophanes fasciatus* (Billberg, 1817)**

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Ivory Coast, Sierra Leone, Tanzania, Zambia (Schönherr 1817a; Villiers 1959; Mourglia et Teocci 1994; Adlbauer 2000; Delahaye 2009; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VI.2020.

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Plectogasterini**31. *Plectogaster jordani* Heath, 1905**

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Liberia, Nigeria, Togo,

Sierra Leone (Heath 1905; Adlbauer et Delahaye 2006; Meunier 2007; Bouyer 2017; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, 15.VI.2016; Sikasso, VIII.2015.

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Phoracanthini

32. *Cordylomera spinicornis nitidipennis* Audinet-Serville, 1834

Distribution in Africa: the Gambia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Mali, Nigeria, Senegal, Sudan (Audinet-Serville 1833; Duffy 1952; Villiers 1962; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Kara, 30.II.1957 (Villiers 1962).

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Callichromatini

33. *Philematium festivum* (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Cameroon, Central African Republic, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Liberia, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo, Uganda and Mali (**new record**); also recorded from Guadeloupe (Fabricius 1775; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Kenieroba, VI.2016.

34. *Hintziellus plagiatus* (Dalman, 1817)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Prosyne tenellus* Bates, 1879

Distribution in Africa: Ivory Coast, Guinea, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Togo (Schönherr 1817; Bates 1879; Juhel 2020; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015; Ouronina, VIII.2020.

35. *Guitelia vuilleti* Oberthür, 1911

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Locustipes saltator* Heller, 1919

Distribution in Africa: Ghana, Mali, Sudan, Togo (Oberthür 1911; Heller 1919; Quentin et Villiers 1971; Quentin et Villiers 1972).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Quentin et Villiers 1971; Quentin et Villiers 1972).

36. *Helymaeus tricolor* (Guérin-Ménéville, 1840)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Closteromerus Raffrayi* Fairmaire, 1882
- = *Helymaeus pallidiventris* Jordan, 1894
- = *Helymaeus erlangeri* Schmidt, 1922
- = *Helymaeus testaceiventris* subsp. *rufescens* Schmidt, 1923
- = *Helymaeus Bayeri* Burgeon, 1931

Distribution in Africa: Burkina Faso, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Mali, Senegal, Somali, South Africa, Tanzania (Guérin-Ménéville 1840; Fairmaire 1882c; Jordan 1894; Schmidt 1922; Schmidt 1923; Burgeon 1931; Juhel et Bentanachs 2009; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Juhel et Bentanachs 2009; Adlbauer et Beck 2015).

37. *Oxyprosopus coeruleus* (Olivier, 1790)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Promeces jucundus* Guérin-Ménéville, 1840
- = *Cerambyx Fabricii* Dalman, 1817
- = *Oxyprosopus Jucundus* Thomson, 1864

Distribution in Africa: Guinea, Liberia, Mali, Senegal, Sierra Leone (Olivier 1790; Dalman 1817; Guérin-Ménéville 1840; Thomson 1864; Schmidt 1922; Juhel 2017; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Juhel 2017).

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Achrysonini**38. *Allogaster geniculatus* Thomson, 1864**

Distribution in Africa: Ivory Coast, Senegal (Thomson 1864; Adlbauer 2000; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Kenieroba, VI.2016.

Subfamily Cerambycinae, Tribe Trachyderini**39. *Purpuricenus decorus* (Olivier, 1800)**

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Acanthopterus tripunctatus* Gory, 1844

- = *Philagathes Duchaussoyi* Théry, 1893
- = *Purpuricenus decorus* var. *Theryi* Lepesme, 1948
- = *Purpuricenus decorus* var. *Lafertei* Lepesme, 1948
- = *Purpuricenus decorus* var. *Lhotei* Lepesme, 1948

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Mali, Nigeria, Senegal (Olivier 1800; Gory 1844; Théry 1893; Aurivillius 1912; Lepesme 1948; Bjørnstad 2019; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Bjørnstad 2019).

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Sternotomini

40. *Zographus regalis* (Brown, 1776)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Zographus regalis* ab. *cuprea* Breuning, 1935
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Poleti* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Poleti* ab. *viridisparsus* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Poleti* ab. *viridiventris* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Poleti* ab. *viridicollis* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Dyoti* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Boni* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *sangaensis* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Marquei* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *dahomeyensis* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Favareli* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Favareli* ab. *pseudocuprea* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Favareli* ab. *viridimarginatus* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis* s.-sp. *Favareli* ab. *viridiventris* Le Moul, 1939
- = *Zographus regalis centralis* Allard, 1993

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Gabon, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Zambia (Brown 1776; Le Moul 1939; Breuning 1959; Breuning 1965a; Allard 1993; Mourglia et Teocchi 1994; Adlbauer et Mourglia 1999; Delahaye 2009; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015.

41. *Freadelpha eremita* (Westwood, 1845)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Freadelpha humeralis* Thomson, 1858

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Benin, Cameroon, Central African Republic, DR Congo, Ivory Coast, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo, Zambia (Westwood 1845; Thomson 1858; Allard 1993; Delahaye 2009; Teocchi et al. 2015; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, 15.VI.2016; Sikasso, VIII.2015.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Phrynetini

42. *Eurysops esau* Chevrolat, 1855

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Phryneteta buphthalmus* White, 1858

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, DR Congo, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, (Chevrolat 1855; White 1858; Breuning 1937; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

43. *Phryneteta spinator* Fabricius, 1792

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Cerambyx obscurus* Olivier, 1795

= *Lamia Sterilis* Schönherr, 1817

= *Phryneteta tristis* Thomson, 1878

= *Phryneteta obscura* var. *Ugandae* Aurivillius, 1914

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Benin, Burundi, Congo, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Liberia, Malawi, Mozambique, Niger, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe and Mali (**new record**); also recorded from Madagascar (Fabricius 1792; Olivier 1795; Schönherr 1817b; Thomson 1878; Aurivillius 1914; Teocchi et al. 2013; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

44. *Stenophryneteta variegata* Aurivillius, 1907

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Stenophryneteta cinerea* Aurivillius, 1907

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Cameroon, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Malawi, Mozambique, Senegal, Tanzania, Zambia, Zimbabwe (Aurivillius 1907; Teocchi et Sudre 2002; Delahaye 2009; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Prosopocerini

45. *Bangalaia nebulosa* (Quedenfeldt, 1887)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Anybostetha Quedenfeldti* Duvivier, 1892
- = *Agnitogaster variegatus* Jordan, 1894
- = *Prosopocera (Dalterus) Vaneyeni* Breuning, 1951

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Central African Republic, DR Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Guinea, Ivory Coast, (Quedenfeldt 1887; Duvivier 1892b; Jordan 1894; Breuning 1951a; Lepesme et Breuning 1956; Breuning et Teocchi 1975b; Cools 1993; Teocchi et al. 2009; Teocchi et al. 2010; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

46. *Prosopocera (Dalterus) inermis* Aurivillius, 1891

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Prosopocera lutulenta* Gahan, 1894
- = *Prosopocera minor* Hintz, 1909
- = *Prosopocera (Timoreticus) inermis* ab. *viridescens* Breuning, 1936
- = *Prosopocera (Dalterus) madagascariensis* Breuning, 1965
- = *Prosopocera (Alphitopola) leucomarmorata* Breuning, 1966
- = *Prosopocera (Dalterus) alboampliata* Breuning, 1981
- = *Prosopocera* (s.s.) *serowensis* Breuning, 1986

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Botswana, Chad, DC Congo, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Namibia, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe; also recorded from Madagascar (Aurivillius 1891; Gahan 1894; Hintz 1909; Breuning 1936a; Villiers 1962; Breuning 1965b; Breuning 1966; Breuning 1981b; Breuning 1986; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 16.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962).

47. *Prosopocera antennata* Gahan, 1890

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Prosopocera falcata* Distant, 1898
- = *Prosopocera (Prosopocera) antennata* m. *quadrimaculata* Breuning, 1936
- = *Prosopocera tricornis* Breuning, 1960
- = *Prosopocera* (s. str.) *allardi* Breuning, 1964
- = *Prosopocera (Dalterus) tchadensis* Breuning, 1967
- = *Prosopocera* (s. s.) *paratchadensis* Breuning, 1967
- = *Prosopocera (Parapocera) decelliana* Breuning, 1968

- = *Prosopocera* (s. s.) *hintzi* m. *expressior* Breuning, 1969
- = *Prosopocera* (*Prosopocera*) *pseudotchadensis* Breuning, 1981
- = *Prosopocera* (s.s.) *antennata* ssp. *orientalis* Breuning, 1986
- = *Prosopocera* (s.s.) *forchhammeri* Breuning, 1986

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Chad, Central African Republic, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Ghana, Guinea, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Zambia (Gahan 1890; Distant 1898; Breuning 1936a; Breuning 1960; Breuning 1964; Breuning 1967b; Breuning 1968a; Breuning 1969; Breuning 1981a; Forchhammer et Breuning 1986; Adlbauer et Mourglia 1999; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015.

48. *Prosopocera aemilii* Aurivillius, 1907

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Prosopocera Aemilii* Aurivillius, 1907
- = *Prosopocera* (*Alphitopola*) *aemilii* ab. *viridissima* Breuning, 1936
- = *Prosopocera* (*Alphitopola*) *aemilii* ab. *ochrescens* Breuning, 1936
- = *Prosopocera* (*Alphitopola*) *aemilii* ab. *albida* Breuning, 1936
- = *Prosopocera* (*Alphitopola*) *aemilii* ab. *annulata* Breuning, 1936
- = *Prosopocera* (*Alphitopola*) *parajeanneli* Breuning, 1978

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, Benin, DR Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Ghana, Ivory Coast (Aurivillius 1907; Breuning 1936a; Breuning 1978b; Teocchi 2000b; Teocchi et al. 2004; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VI.2016.

49. *Prosopocera nivosa* (Fairmaire, 1897)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Alphitopola assimilis* Gahan, 1898

Distribution in Africa: Kenya, Somali, Tanzania (Fairmaire 1897; Gahan 1898; Teocchi 1989; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

Taxonomic note: Uncertain determination.

50. *Prosopocera lactator* (Fabricius, 1801)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Lamia Radiata* Gory, 1835

- = *Prosopocera plagiatrix* Kolbe, 1893
- = *Prosopocera (Prosopocera) lactator* ab. *Duponti* Aurivillius, 1922
- = *Prosopocera (Prosopocera) lactator* m. *femoralis* Breuning, 1936
- = *Prosopocera lactator* v. *posticereducta* Lepesme, 1952
- = *Prosopocera* (s. s.) *lactator* v. *lundae* Lepesme, 1953
- = *Prosopocera* (s. str.) *lactator* v. *intermedia* Gilmour, 1956

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Benin, Botswana, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo Ethiopia, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe (Fabricius 1801; Gory 1835; Kolbe 1893b; Aurivillius 1922; Breuning 1936a; Lepesme 1952b; Lepesme 1953a; Gilmour 1956a; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 1956 (Villiers 1962).

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Ceroplesini

51. *Ceroplesis aestuans* (Olivier, 1800)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Ceroplesis aestuans* sbsp. *guineensis* Hintz, 1920
- = *Ceroplesis aestuans* sbsp. *ornata* Hintz, 1920
- = *Ceroplesis aestuans senegalensis* Fiedler, 1938
- = *Ceroplesis aestuans dakarensis* Fiedler, 1938
- = *Ceroplesis aestuans nigerica* Fiedler, 1938
- = *Ceroplesis aestuans ubangiensis* Fiedler, 1938
- = *Ceroplesis aestuans* v. *aegyptiacus* Gilmour, 1956

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Cameroon, Chad, Central African Republic, DR Congo, Egypt, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Morocco, Niger, Senegal, Sudan, Togo, Uganda (Olivier 1800; Hintz 1920; Fiedler 1938; Gilmour 1956a; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: San (Villiers 1962).

52. *Ceroplesis buettneri* (Kolbe, 1893)

Distribution in Africa: the Gambia, Ivory Coast, Senegal, Togo (Kolbe 1893a; Lepsme 1953b; Adlbauer 1993; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Tragocephalini

53. *Isochariesthes lesnei sudanica* Breuning, 1962

Distribution in Africa: Central African Republic, Chad, Ivory Coast, Mali, Senegal (Breuning 1962b; Villiers 1962; Teocchi 1997a; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré (Breuning 1962b); Boré, 14.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962); Ouronina, VIII.2020 (original data).

54. *Graciella pulchella* (Klug, 1835)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Chariesthes concinnus* Chevrolat, 1858
- = *Chariesthes senegalensis* Chevrolat, 1858
- = *Chariesthes elegantulus* Chevrolat, 1858
- = *Graciella pulchella* v. *fasciata* Gilmour, 1956

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Cameroun, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Liberia, Nigeria, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Togo, Uganda (Chevrolat 1858; Lepesme 1950; Gilmour 1956; Breuning et Teocchi 1981; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Ancyлонotini

55. *Ancyлонotus tribulus* (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Gabon, the Gambia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe (Fabricius 1775; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer 1993; Adlbauer et Mourglia 1999; Delahaye 2009; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Trócoli 2020; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962); Ouronina, VI.2020 (original data).

56. *Lasiopezus variegator* (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution in Africa: Cameroun, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Niger, Senegal, Togo (Breuning et Teocchi 1981; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VI.2020.

57. *Lasiopezus nigromaculatus* Quedenfeldt, 1882

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Lasiopezus ambiguus* Kolbe, 1900

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Botswana, Cameroon, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Zimbabwe (Quedenfeldt 1882; Kolbe 1900; Adlbauer 2018; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

58. *Idactus cristulatus* (Fairmaire, 1886)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Lasiopezus exiguus* Quedenfeldt, 1891

= *Idactus matabelicus* Aurivillius, 1916

= *Idactus assimilis* Breuning, 1938

= *Idactus fuscovittatus* Breuning, 1971

= *Idactus paralateralis* Breuning, 1986

Distribution in Africa: Botswana, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Djibouti, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Zimbabwe and Mali (**new record**); also recorded from Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen (Fairmaire 1886; Quedenfeldt 1891; Aurivillius 1916; Breuning 1938b; Breuning 1971b; Breuning 1986; Sudre et Teocchi 2002; Teocchi et al. 2010; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VI.2020.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Pteropliini

59. *Sthenias cylindrator* (Fabricius, 1801)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Stenias Mionii* Guérin-Méneville, 1840

= *Stenias verticalis* Chevrolat, 1857

= *Chalarus leucaspis* Fähræus, 1872

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Botswana, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Liberia, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zimbabwe and Mali (**new record**); also recorded

from Martinique (Fabricius 1801; Guérin-Méneville 1840; Chevrolat 1857a; Fåhraeus 1872; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Sudre et al. 2018; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Kangaba, 3–7.VII.2016.

60. *Pteroträgula leucoloma* (Lapote de Castelnau, 1840)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Hatlia leucocincta* Guérin-Méneville, 1844

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Cameroon, Chad, Ivory Coast, Mali, Senegal (Lapote de Castelnau 1840; Guérin-Méneville 1844; Lepesme 1952; Villiers 1962; Teocchi 1985; Teocchi et al. 2014a; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo, région de Macina (Lepesme 1952); Boré, 26.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962).

61. *Niphoträgulus occidentalis* Breuning, 1977

Distribution in Africa: Endemic in Mali (Breuning 1977; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Koulikoro (Breuning 1977).

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Apomecyni

62. *Apomecyna binubila* Pascoe, 1858

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Apomecyna macularia* Harold, 1879

= *Apomecyna binubila* m. *conjuncta* Breuning, 1953

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Benin, Botswana, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Zambia, Zimbabwe (Pascoe 1858; Harold 1879; Breuning 1953b; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

63. *Apomecyna lameerei* (Pic, 1895)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Apomecyna arabica* Breuning, 1938

= *Apomecyna arabica* ssp. *Mateui* Breuning, 1953

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Egypt, Mali, Mauritania, Morocco, Senegal, Western Sahara; also recorded from Iran, Iraq, Israel, Pakistan, Oman, Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Yemen (Pic 1895; Breuning 1938c; Breuning 1953b; Lepesme et Breuning 1955a; Villiers 1962; Sama 2008; Löbl et Smetana 2010; Ambrus et Grosser 2012; Trócoli 2020; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 13.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962).

64. *Enaretta varia* (Pascoe, 1886)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Enaretta fasciculata* Hintz, 1919

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Botswana, Cameroon, Central African Republic, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mozambique, South Africa, Tanzania, Zambia (Pascoe 1886; Hintz 1919; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Kangaba, 3–7.VII.2016.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Agapanthiini

65. *Hyllisia ochreovittata* Breuning, 1940

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Chad, DR Congo, the Gambia, Ivory Coast, Mali, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Tanzania, Uganda (Breuning 1940b; Lepesme et Breuning 1955a; Villiers 1962; Teocchi et al. 2009; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Diafarabé; Macina (Villiers 1962).

66. *Pseudohippopsis filiformis* (Olivier, 1800)

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Central African Republic, Ethiopia, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Mali, Senegal, Somalia, Sudan, Tanzania, Zimbabwe (Olivier 1800; Guérin-Méneville 1840; Breuning 1940b; Lepesme 1952a; Adlbauer et Beck 2015).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo, région de Macina (Lepesme 1952).

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Saperdini

67. *Nupserha basalis* (Erichson, 1843)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Sphenura occipitalis* Chevrolat, 1857

= *Nupserha basipennis* Fairmaire, 1887

- = *Nupserha basalis* var. *Ugandae* Aurivillius, 1914
- = *Nupserha angulata* Aurivillius, 1914
- = *Nupserha ventralis* Hintz, 1919 (nec Gahan, 1894)
- = *Stibara sexmaculata* Pic, 1943
- = *Nupserha bidentata* m. *subbasipennis* Breuning, 1950
- = *Nupserha bidentata* m. *immaculicollis* Breuning, 1950
- = *Nupserha apicalis* m. *capensis* Breuning, 1950
- = *Nupserha bidentata* v. *quadripunctata* Lepesme et Breuning, 1952
- = *Nupserha bidentata* var. *joveri* Lepesme et Breuning, 1953
- = *Nupserha bidentata* ssp. *urundiensis* Breuning, 1955
- = *Nupserha bidentata* m. *senegalensis* Breuning, 1956
- = *Nupserha bidentata* m. *nigrosternalis* Breuning, 1956
- = *Nupserha basalis* ssp. *basipennis* var. *laterimacula* Breuning, 1958
- = *Nupserha bidentata* ssp. *urundiensis* var. *kenyana* Breuning, 1958
- = *Nupserha basalis* ssp. *angulata* m. *ituriensis* Breuning, 1971
- = *Nupserha basalis* m. *atrata* Teocchi, 1994
- = *Nupserha basalis* m. *infranigra* Teocchi, 1997

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, DR Congo, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda and Mali (**new record**); also recorded from India (Erichson 1843; Chevrolat 1857b; Fairmaire 1887a; Aurivillius 1914; Hintz 1919; Pic 1943; Breuning 1950b; Breuning 1950c; Lepesme et Breuning 1952; Lepesme et Breuning 1953; Breuning 1955; Breuning 1956a; Breuning 1958a; Breuning 1971a; Teocchi 1994; Teocchi 1997b; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015.

68. *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) cylindricollis* (Kolbe, 1893)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Blepisanis geniculata* Kolbe, 1893
- = *Blepisanis flaviceps* Aurivillius, 1925
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) geniculata* m. *subternigra* Breuning, 1950
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) geniculata* m. *flaviventris* Breuning, 1950
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) geniculata* m. *sassensis* Breuning, 1950
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) geniculata* m. *rufolateralis* Breuning, 1950
- = *Phytæcia geniculata* m. *pusilla* Breuning, 1950
- = *Phytæcia geniculata* m. *fuscibasicornis* Breuning, 1950
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) Kolbei* m. *togoensis* Breuning, 1951
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) Kolbei* m. *Lamottei* Breuning, 1951
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) Kolbei* m. *rufoantennata* Breuning, 1951
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) kolbei* v. *flavoabdominalis* Lepesme et Breuning, 1952

- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) kolbei* v. *nigroscutellata* Lepesme et Breuning, 1952
- = *Phytæcia (Pseudoblepisanis) Kolbei* m. *Massarti* Breuning, 1953
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) Kolbei* m. *rufoampliata* Breuning, 1953
- = *Phytæcia (Pseudoblepisanis) kolbei* m. *atroampliata* Breuning, 1953
- = *Phytoecia (Pseudoblepisanis) kolbei* m. *rubriscapa* Breuning, 1970

Distribution in Africa: Congo, DR Congo, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Togo (Kolbe 1893a; Aurivillius 1925a; Breuning 1950b; Breuning 1950c; Breuning 1951b; Lepesme et Breuning 1952; Breuning 1953a; Breuning 1953c; Breuning 1967c; Breuning 1970; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Astathini

69. *Hecphora testator* (Fabricius, 1781)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Hecphora nitida* Aurivillius, 1920

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, DR Congo, the Gambia, Ivory Coast, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo, Uganda (Fabricius 1781; Aurivillius 1920; Lepesme 1950; Breuning 1956b; Lepesme 1957; Adlbauer 1993; Teocchi et al. 1994; Sudre et Jiroux 2014; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Kenieroba, VI.2016

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Desmiphorini

70. *Sophronica sudanica* Breuning, 1962

Distribution in Africa: Endemic in Mali (Breuning 1962b; Villiers 1962; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Farimake, Koubita (Breuning 1962b); Farimaké – Koubita (Villiers 1962).

71. *Sophronica ventralis* Aurivillius, 1925

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Sophronica curta* Breuning, 1939

Distribution in Africa: Congo, DR Congo, Ghana, Kenya, Mali, Nigeria, Tanzania, Uganda, Zimbabwe (Aurivillius 1925b; Breuning 1939a; Breuning 1963; Teocchi et al. 2016).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Teocchi et al. 2016).

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Mesosini

72. *Coptops aedificator* (Fabricius, 1793)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Lamia ambulator* Fabricius, 1775
- = *Lamia fusca* Olivier, 1797
- = *Lamia villica* Olivier, 1797
- = *Lachnia parallela* Audinet-Serville, 1835
- = *Coptops quadristigma* Fåhraeus, 1872
- = *Phymasterna inhambanensis* Bertoloni, 1876
- = *Coptops bidens* Wollaston, 1877

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Central African Republic, Djibouti, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Gabon, the Gambia, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Liberia, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe and Mali (**new record**); also recorded from Andaman Islands, Cape Verde, China, Comoros, Hawaii, India, Madagascar, Mauritius, Oman, Pakistan, the Philippines, Réunion, Saudi Arabia, Seychelles, Sri Lanka, St. Helena, Taiwan, Yemen (Fabricius 1775; Fabricius 1793; Olivier 1797; Audinet-Serville 1835; Fåhraeus 1872; Bertoloni 1876; Wollaston 1877; Saha et al. 2013; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Kariyanna et al. 2017; Kahuthia-Gatu et al. 2019; Rapuzzi et al. 2019; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Kenieroba, VI.2016.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Crossotini

73. *Corus pseudocostiger* Breuning, 1936

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Guinea-Bissau, Ivory Coast, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda (Breuning 1936b; Breuning 1942a; Adlbauer 1998; Adlbauer et Mourglia 1999; Teocchi et al. 2009; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015

74. *Crossotus albicollis* Guérin-Méneville, 1844

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Crossotides obtusus* Hintz, 1912
- = *Crossotus senegalensis* Breuning, 1950

Distribution in Africa: Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Mali, Mauretania, Morocco, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal (Guérin-Méneville 1844; Hintz 1912; Breuning 1950a; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Kenieroba, VI.2016

75. *Crossotus plumicornis* Audinet-Serville, 1835

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Crossotus Natalensis* White, 1858
- = *Crossotus vestiticornis* Fairmaire, 1882
- = *Crossotus plumicornis* subsp. *damarensis* Hintz, 1912
- = *Crossotus excavatipennis* Breuning, 1961

Distribution in Africa: Botswana, Burkina Faso, Chad, Congo, DR Congo, Eritrea, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mauretania, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe (Audinet-Serville 1835; White 1858; Fairmaire 1882a; Hintz 1912; Breuning 1961; Villiers 1962; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Farimaké – Dioura, 13.VIII.1954 (Villiers 1962).

76. *Crossotus stigmaticus* (Fåhraeus, 1872)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Frea* (*Crossotofrea*) *fasciculata* Breuning, 1981

Distribution in Africa: Botswana, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, South Africa, Tanzania (Fåhraeus 1872; Lepesme 1952a; Breuning 1981a; Sudre et al. 2007; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo, région de Macina (Lepesme, 1952).

77. *Crossotus sublineatus* Gestro, 1892

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Crossotus* (*Crossotides*) *sennaariensis* Hintz, 1912
- = *Crossotus Marshalli* Breuning, 1935
- = *Crossotus sahariensis* Breuning, 1938
- = *Crossotus somaliensis* Breuning, 1972

Distribution in Africa: Algeria, Chad, Djibouti, Ethiopia, Kenya, Mali, Morocco, Mauritania, Niger, Somalia, Sudan (Gestro 1892; Hintz 1912; Breuning 1935; Breuning 1938b; Breuning 1972; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Sudre et al. 2007; Adlbauer et Beck 2015).

78. *Crossotus subocellatus* (Fairmaire, 1886)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Crossotus Phillipsi* Gahan, 1896

= *Crossotus* (*Crossotides*) *Heimschi* Peyerimhoff, 1922

Distribution in Africa: Algeria, Chad, Djibouti, Egypt, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Libya, Mali, Morocco, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Somalia, Sudan, Tanzania; also recorded from Oman, Saudi Arabia (Fairmaire 1886; Gahan 1896; Peyerimhoff 1922; Sudre et al. 2007; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Sudre et al. 2007; Adlbauer et Beck 2015).

79. *Crossotus tubericollis* (Fairmaire, 1891)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Crossotus robustus* Jordan, 1894

= *Crossotus bimaculatus* Aurivillius, 1903

= *Crossotus albomaculatus* var. *vittatus* Aurivillius, 1914

Distribution in Africa: Benin, Cameroon, Central African Republic, DR Congo, Eritrea, Ethiopia, the Gambia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Malawi, Mali, Morocco, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia (Fairmaire 1891; Jordan 1894; Aurivillius 1903; Aurivillius 1914; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962).

80. *Epidichostates strandi* (Breuning, 1935)

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Crossotus sassensis* Breuning, 1935

Distribution in Africa: Benin, DR Congo, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Sierra Leone (Breuning 1935; Sudre et al. 2007; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Sikasso, VIII.2015

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Eunidiini**81. *Eunidia kristenseni* Aurivillius, 1911**

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Eunidia kristenseni* m. *albida* Breuning, 1940

- = *Eunidia kristenseni* ab. *flavomaculata* Breuning, 1942
- = *Eunidia kristenseni* m. *arabica* Breuning, 1962

Distribution in Africa: Botswana, Chad, Djibouti, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mali, Namibia, Niger, Senegal, Somalia, Sudan, Tanzania; also recorded from Oman, Saudi Arabia, Yemen (Aurivillius 1911; Breuning 1940a; Breuning 1942c; Breuning 1962a; Villiers 1962; Ambrus et Grosser 2012; Teocchi et al. 2014b; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 7.VIII.1956 (Villiers 1962).

82. *Eunidia flavoapicata* Breuning, 1939

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Eunidia apicefulva* Breuning, 1953

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Mali, Nigeria, Somali, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda (Breuning 1938a; Breuning 1939b; Breuning 1953b; Villiers 1962; Teocchi 2000a; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Teocchi et al. 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 17.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962).

83. *Eunidia caffra* Fåhraeus, 1872

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Eunidia lurida* Fåhraeus, 1872
- = *Eunidia modesta* Gahan, 1904
- = *Eunidia albisparsa* Breuning, 1938
- = *Eunidia collarti* Breuning, 1948
- = *Eunidia rufifrons* Breuning, 1954
- = *Eunidia paraflavicans* Breuning, 1971
- = *Eunidia grisea* Breuning, 1986

Distribution in Africa: Botswana, DR Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Mozambique, Somalia, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zimbabwe (Fåhraeus 1872; Gahan 1904; Distant 1904–1906; Breuning 1938d; Breuning 1948; Breuning 1954; Villiers 1962; Breuning 1971b; Breuning 1986; Adlbauer 1997; Teocchi 2000; Teocchi et al. 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Dogo (Villiers 1962).

84. *Eunidia similis* Breuning, 1942

Distribution in Africa: Cameroon, Central African Republic, Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Togo (Breuning 1942b; Teocchi 2000a; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VIII.2020.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Acanthocinini**85. *Exocentrus (Pseudocentrus) girardi* Breuning et Teocchi, 1975**

Distribution in Africa: Ivory Coast (Breuning et Teocchi 1975a; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Kenieroba, VI.2016.

86. *Exocentrus (Ispaterus) mirei* Lepesme et Breuning, 1955

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Exocentrus crassepunctus* Lepesme et Breuning, 1955
- = *Exocentrus (Camptomyme) rufotibialis* Breuning, 1957
- = *Exocentrus (Pseudocentrus) demangei* Breuning, 1962
- = *Exocentrus* (s. s.) *rufohumeralis* Breuning, 1967 (nec Breuning, 1957)
- = *Exocentrus (Pseudocentrus) rufohumeralis* Breuning, 1972 (nec Breuning, 1957)
- = *Exocentrus (Camptomyme) rufipennis* Breuning, 1974
- = *Exocentrus (Camptomyme) fuscipes* Breuning, 1981
- = *Exocentrus (Camptomyme) paravariegatus* Breuning, 1981
- = *Exocentrus (Pseudocentrus) neubeckeri* Breuning, 1981

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Central African Republic, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mali, Niger, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania (Lepesme et Breuning 1955a; Breuning 1957b; Breuning 1962b; Breuning 1967a; Breuning 1968b; Breuning 1974a; Breuning 1977; Breuning 1981a; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Boré, 13.VII.1956 (Villiers 1962).

87. *Exocentrus (Pseudocentrus) chevaugeni* Lepesme et Breuning, 1955

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Exocentrus (Camptomyme) decorsei* Breuning, 1958

Distribution in Africa: Chad, Ivory Coast, Malawi, Mali, Niger, Senegal, Rwanda, Uganda (Lepesme et Breuning 1955b; Breuning 1958b; Breuning 1963; Sudre et Teocchi 2002; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Unknown (Breuning, 1963).

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Dorcasomatini**88. *Olenecamptus macari* Lameere, 1892**

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

- = *Olenecamptus macari* ssp. *insularis* Breuning, 1960

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Bioko Island, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Congo, DR Congo, Guinea, Ivory Coast, Uganda (Lameere 1892; Breuning 1960; Breuning et Teocchi 1981; Teocchi et al. 2010; Tavakilian 2022) and Mali (**new record**).

Collection site in Mali: Ouronina, VI.2020.

Subfamily Lamiinae, Tribe Apomecynini

89. *Enaretta castelnaudii* Thomson, 1864

Synonymy follows Tavakilian 2022:

= *Phoryctus mucoreus* Gerstaecker, 1871

= *Enaretta intermedia* Aurivillius, 1925

= *Fouquetia fasciculata* Pic, 1932

Distribution in Africa: Angola, Benin, Botswana, Chad, Egypt, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Mali, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe (Thomson 1864; Gerstaecker 1871; Aurivillius 1925b; Pic 1932; Breuning et Teocchi 1978; Adlbauer et Beck 2015; Tavakilian 2022).

Collection site in Mali: Bamako (Pic 1932).

Discussion

Presently 89 species of Ceramycidae are known from Mali, 42 of them are new records. Being aware of the patchy collection efforts and the lack of material from the most southern regions of the country we expect a significant number of additional species which are so far not recorded. Among the recorded species 2 are suggested to be endemic to Mali, 8 show a West African distribution, 64 species are widely distributed on the continent, while 15 species are also known from outside of the continent.

All in all, little material from the West African Sahel can be found in international and local collections. Much work needs to be done to understand distribution patterns and ecological needs for almost all species. We would not be surprised if so far much less than 50% of the local species have been recorded. Mali is from a point of biodiversity one of the least researched countries (115th place in the world and 31st place in sub-Saharan Africa; Wolf et al. 2022). Even in the best-researched group of insects, butterflies, there is not a single publication dedicated to the local fauna and only a few dozen of species were according to Larsen (2005) sporadically recorded without any attempt to publish a local fauna. The authors of this study meanwhile compiled a list of more than 150 species of butterflies from Mali with minimal effort, the total number of local species should be again far above this number (original unpublished data). The same is the case for moths; only a few dozens of noctuid species are published while we compiled a preliminary list of more than 250 morphospecies

(original unpublished data). It can be expected that this situation is similar to most other invertebrate groups. The lack of data can easily be explained by only a few entomologists having collected in Mali, only over short periods, during the last decades. This resulted in the false assumption that biodiversity is low in this “arid” country which even further discouraged potential research on the local fauna and biodiversity. The ecosystems in the Sahelian belt and the deciduous scattered forests towards the south are presently threatened by rapid climate change with resulting desertification (FAO UN / UN EP 2020). This is especially the case in the Western Sahel and particularly in Mali with one of the highest population growth rates within Africa (8th place in the world with 2.9% annual population growth; World Bank 2022). There seems to be only a short window in which the present biodiversity can be recorded in these threatened and vanishing ecosystems and valuable data can be preserved for future generations and long-term projects measuring the changes in the local ecosystems over the next decades.

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